
USER SATISFACTION QUESTIONNAIRE

Please rate your agreement with the following statements on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 represents *Strongly Disagree* and 5 represents *Strongly Agree*.

The concept of properties

I know the concept of deadlock

1. (Strongly Disagree)
2. (Disagree)
3. (Neutral)
4. (Agree)
5. (Strongly Agree)

I know the concept of model consistency

1. (Strongly Disagree)
2. (Disagree)
3. (Neutral)
4. (Agree)
5. (Strongly Agree)

I know the concept of safety property

1. (Strongly Disagree)
2. (Disagree)
3. (Neutral)
4. (Agree)
5. (Strongly Agree)

I know the concept of compliance between different viewpoints

1. (Strongly Disagree)
2. (Disagree)
3. (Neutral)
4. (Agree)
5. (Strongly Agree)

Identification of deadlock

I know how to identify a deadlock in an architectural description without using a tool

1. (Strongly Disagree)
2. (Disagree)
3. (Neutral)
4. (Agree)
5. (Strongly Agree)

I could identify that the SysADL tool verified the occurrence of deadlock by analyzing an architectural description

1. (Strongly Disagree)
2. (Disagree)
3. (Neutral)
4. (Agree)
5. (Strongly Agree)

I could identify that the SysADL tool verified the occurrence of deadlock-freedom by analyzing an architectural description

1. (Strongly Disagree)
2. (Disagree)
3. (Neutral)
4. (Agree)

5. (Strongly Agree)

Identification of inconsistencies and non-compliance between behavioral and execution viewpoints

I know how to identify a model inconsistency in an architectural description, without using a tool

1. (Strongly Disagree)
2. (Disagree)
3. (Neutral)
4. (Agree)
5. (Strongly Agree)

I know how to identify the compliance between behavioral and execution viewpoints in an architectural description, without using a tool

1. (Strongly Disagree)
2. (Disagree)
3. (Neutral)
4. (Agree)
5. (Strongly Agree)

I could identify that the SysADL tool verified the occurrence of model inconsistency by analyzing an architecture description

1. (Strongly Disagree)
2. (Disagree)
3. (Neutral)
4. (Agree)
5. (Strongly Agree)

I could identify that the SysADL tool verified the occurrence of no inconsistencies by analyzing an architecture description

1. (Strongly Disagree)
2. (Disagree)
3. (Neutral)
4. (Agree)
5. (Strongly Agree)

I could identify that the SysADL tool verified the occurrence of compliance issues between behavioral and execution viewpoints by analyzing an architecture description

1. (Strongly Disagree)
2. (Disagree)
3. (Neutral)
4. (Agree)
5. (Strongly Agree)

I could identify that the SysADL tool verified the occurrence of compliance between behavioral and execution viewpoints by analyzing an architecture description

1. (Strongly Disagree)
2. (Disagree)
3. (Neutral)
4. (Agree)
5. (Strongly Agree)

Identification of safety issues

I know how to identify a safety issue in an architectural description without using a tool.

1. (Strongly Disagree)
2. (Disagree)
3. (Neutral)
4. (Agree)

5. (Strongly Agree)

I could identify that the SysADL tool verified the occurrence of safety issues by analyzing an architecture description.

1. (Strongly Disagree)
2. (Disagree)
3. (Neutral)
4. (Agree)
5. (Strongly Agree)

I could identify that the SysADL tool verified the occurrence of no safety issues according to the safety properties defined by analyzing an architecture description.

1. (Strongly Disagree)
2. (Disagree)
3. (Neutral)
4. (Agree)
5. (Strongly Agree)

Tool usability

In case of an invalid property, the tool provides clear information to the user to identify the error in the architecture description

1. (Strongly Disagree)
2. (Disagree)
3. (Neutral)
4. (Agree)
5. (Strongly Agree)

I have no difficulty using the SysADL tool

1. (Strongly Disagree)
2. (Disagree)
3. (Neutral)
4. (Agree)
5. (Strongly Agree)

Additional comments

Please provide any additional comments or suggestions regarding your experience with the SysADL tool and the tasks you performed in this study. This field is optional.